

The Role of Cadres in Providing Prevention of Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) in Bandung City

Yosef Pandai Lolan

Bachelor Program in Public Health, Bhakti Kencana University, Bandung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The number of dengue fever incidents in 2020 was 111, a decrease compared to the year previously it was 45 Bandung City Health Profile in 2020, 176 per 100,000 population. Proportion type sex dengue fever cases in 2020 show that cases of dengue fever in men are more Lots compared to women. Type of research This that is a descriptive-analytic qualitative (exploratory study) using a cross-sectional design, Research was carried out in Bandung City, West Java Province. The sampling technique used is non-probability of use Purposive Sampling method where method uses criteria that have been chosen by the researcher in choose sample. The Chi-square test was obtained Where There is a significant relationship between knowledge cadre p-value of 0.070, giving counseling with a p-value of 0.006 with role cadre in give prevention of dengue fever. Related factors with activity prevention fever dengue bleeding is level knowledge cadres and activities counseling. second factor This has enough influence big on activities prevention fever dengue bleeding. Factors that don't relate is inspection flick mosquito because society has capable of doing it yourself in the environment or each other's house

KEYWORDS: Role of Cadres, Prevention , Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF)

INTRODUCTION

Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) still is a problem for health especially since Madi is a temperate country tropical. World Organization (WHO) said in 2017, reported amount Dengue fever cases in America are decreasing in a way significant by 73%, from 2,177,171 in 2016 to 584,263 cases, apart from Panama, Peru, and Aruba are the countries listed with enhancement cases in 2017. In 2020 fever bloody will continue to hit several countries, namely Bangladesh, Brazil, and Indonesia one country that has reported an improvement amount dengue fever (WHO 2020). At the end in 2022 total Dengue cases in Indonesia reached 143,000 cases, with the number most cases of dengue in West Java Province at 36,594, East Java at 13,189 and Central Java at 12,467. whereas the province with number lowest incidence of dengue is the province my shame as many as 96 cases (RI Ministry of Health 2022) . Dengue cases occurred balanced between women (49%) and men (51%). Mostly Dengue cases occurred in the 15-44 year age group (39%). This pattern is different with death due to dengue, which is more dominant in women (55%) and in older age groups, namely 5-14 years (45%) (Kemenkes RI 2022). As many as 2,790 cases of fever bleeding in Bandung in 2020 decreased compared to in 2019 there were 4,424 cases. The number of dengue fever incidents in 2020 was 111, a decrease compared to the year previously it was 45 Bandung City Health Profile in 2020, 176 per 100,000 population. Proportion type sex dengue fever cases in 2020 show that cases of dengue fever in men more Lots compared to woman. Amount cases of dengue fever in men as many as 1,492 cases (53.48%) and women as many as 1,298 cases (46.52%). Proportion type sex the 2019 dengue fever case also shows this comparison similar namely 52.48% (2,322 cases) for men and 47.51% (2,102 cases) for women . Proportion comparison dengue cases based type sex appears on the graph following this . Death due to dengue fever in 2020 occurred as many as 13 deaths decrease One case death compared to year previously namely 14 cases. Death due to dengue fever spread across 11 sub-districts . Although amount death decrease from year Previously, distribution incident death due to dengue fever increased by 2 sub-districts compared to the year previously there were 9 criticisms (JABAR HEALTH OFFICE 2021) . To get the expected results, this PSN activity should be done in a way broad and continuous. The target is all place breeding mosquitoes, like place water storage for needs daily or place natural water reservoir (SUTRIYAWAN 2021). See conditions in the field , the majority community in the environment the is public with age productive so that No few spend _ time outside home to work . People tend to stay at home only in the afternoon until Evening day . Busyness public the make Lots citizens who ignore health environment place stay. Less residents notice things around the house already No used . That thing result development place brood mosquito . Society has reference that the fogging can eradicate dengue fever cases in the environment them , though activity spraying the only will chase away mosquito temporary. Fogging is

The Role of Cadres in Providing Prevention of Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) in Bandung City

done to expel mosquito mature just , where matter This done with squirt malathion liquid uses fogger that will go out to environment form smog so can reach with wide (Dhefiana 2023).

METHOD

Type of research This that is descriptive analytic qualitative (exploratory study) use a cross sectional design which is something study analytics to analyze role cadre in give prevention of disease fever dengue bleeding. Study carried out in Bandung City, West Java Province. The sampling technique used is non-probability of use Purposive Sampling method where this method use criteria that have been chosen by the researcher in choose sample . Criteria election sample divided become criteria inclusion and exclusion . Type of data used in study This namely primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained in a way direct from respondents. Secondary data obtained from Community Health Center. Stage Data processing in the form of editing, coding, scoring, processing and cleaning. Data analyzed interpreted to test proposed hypothesis with stages namely: analysis univariate that is describe the data obtained and complete with mark percentage with purpose of knowing distribution frequency from all variables studied. Analysis bivariate used that is uni Chi Square (X2), and magnitude opportunities used is the Odds Ratio (OR). Where if OR value > 1, meaning factors studied is factor risk .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

Figure 1. Distribution Frequency Respondent

On results distribution respondents found that in part big respondents own low knowledge with mark percentage of 62.2% and value frequency on knowledge tall amounting to 31 degan mark percentage amounting to 37.8%. Meanwhile for respondents cadres who have role active in do prevention of dengue fever with education 63.4%, among cadres who do not active give prevention with mark frequency amounting to 30 respondents with percentage 36.6%. Seen from frequency respondents to the examination flick mosquito cadres do it inspection amounting to 68.3% of the total cadres who did it sebesar 56. Meanwhile for cadres who do not do amounting to 31.7%. Cadres who provide counseling in efforts to prevent dengue fever amounted to 32.9% and frequency cadres who don't give counseling amounting to 55 people with mark percentage amounting to 67.1%.

Table 1. Factors that influence the role of cadres in providing Fogging Education on Prevention Disease DBD in Bandung City

Cadre Role						
Risk Factors	Active		Inactive _		P value	OR (95%CI)
	n	%	n	%		
Knowledge						
Hight	21	67.7	10	32.3	0.070	1,355 (0.529-3.467)
Low	31	60.8	20	39.2		
Larvae Checker						
Do	33	68.9	23	41.1	0.135	0.529 (0.191-1.462)
Not Doing	19	73.1	7	26.9		
Activity Counseling						
Give	16	59.3	11	40.7	0.006	0.768 (0.289 - 1.981)
Not Giving	36	65.5	19	34.5		

The Role of Cadres in Providing Prevention of Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) in Bandung City

Viewed from table 1 above so can explained that cadres who have knowledge active height give prevention with mark the proportions of 21 with percentage 67.7% and knowledgeable low ones don't active give prevention mark the proportions by 20 with percentage 39.2%. The Chi square test was obtained p- value 0.070 (p-value <0.05) where There is significant relationship between knowledge cadre with role cadre in give prevention of dengue fever. Inspection flick active mosquitoes carried out by cadres with with mark percentage amounted to 68.9% and those that did not do inspection flick in a way No active with mark the proportion is 7 with percentage 26.9. Chi square test results obtained The p-value is 0.135 (p-value > 0.05) which illustrates that No There is significant relationship between inspection flick mosquito with role cadre in do prevention dengue fever disease . On activities counseling active cadre give counseling about prevention dengue disease value the proportion is 16 with percentage 59.3%. Whereas cadres who don't active give counseling with percentage 34.5%. Chi square test results were obtained p-value 0.006 (p-value <0.05) where There is significant relationship between activity counseling with role cadre in give prevention of dengue fever .

DISCUSSION

Connection Knowledge With the role of cadres in providing Prevention of DHF in Bandung City

Research results This knowledge cadres are very influential with role cadre in give prevention dengue fever . With good knowledge so perception cadre about Dengue fever is also increasing well , and with good knowledge cadre can give education to the local community. Study This in line with research conducted by (Indah Trisnaniyanti and Dkk. 2010), increasingly tall knowledge so the more perception is high cadre to prevention dengue fever. According to Secular and Blake, knowledge can form experience to perception. People who use perception without knowledge Possible can produce perception normally, but No interpret in a way clear what has they perceive, for example: people who see can describe face somebody but No can recognize who is that person ? Knowledge help recognize various stimuli that appear and then become perception. By general, knowledge each other complete perception. However, in condition certain knowledge can guide senses someone. Knowledge become more role when information sensors weak and not clear, however if sensor information strong and clear, knowledge still influential. Health cadre must own knowledge about dengue fever including signs and symptoms, mosquitoes / vectors, appropriate PSN, methods reporting / coordination If There is case / suspect and method control and prevention of dengue fever, at the same time give information about risky behavior increase incidence of dengue fever (Siyam and Cahyati 2019). If cadre own enhancement knowledge so will increase understanding cadre in do prevention and control of dengue fever (Siyam and Cahyati 2018) .

Connection Inspection Flick With the role of cadres in providing Prevention of DHF in Bandung City

On research This obtained No There is significant relationship between inspection flick mosquito with role cadre in give prevention. This thing because most people already do capable do monitor independent in the environment or respective housing . Study This No in line with research conducted by (Adnan and Siswani 2019) Where There is significant relationship between role cadre jumantik in monitoring flick periodically (PJB) with behavior public in effort prevention dengue fever in the work area Tebet Village . PJB is effort detection early dengue fever transmission as well hinder development beginning from vector dengue fever transmission when done in a way routine and sustainable activity This form do Place breeding mosquito in the home, for example flower pot coasters, dispenser coasters, coasters refrigerator, bathtub /WC, flower vase, place drink birds, etc. Place breeding mosquitoes outside home, for example jar, drum, gutter, place Rainwater / AC water storage, cans used, bottles plastic, used tires, tales fronds, banana fronds, pieces bamboo, plastic, and others (Natalia, Sambuaga, and Pandean 2017) . Key prevention dengue fever is strict monitoring of reporting _ early results monitoring density vector so that taking action No late moment accept report case from location epidemic. Existence jumantik own vital role in eradication of dengue fever due to on duty monitor population mosquito dengue fever transmitter and its larvae. Inspection flick periodically carried out by the jumantik on duty do visit House every 3 months (Pratamawati 2012) . By general, role jumantik assessed Enough succeed in dengue prevention, however there is a number of thing that becomes material evaluation . Experience in the field in do evaluation performance jumantik usually they No give enough information to public regarding dengue fever and its prevention. Motivation to society is also rare given however, this important once for always given and reminded to public about prevention of dengue fever. If this program walk with Good so public will own sufficient knowledge about dengue fever and behavior they controlled (Purnama 2011).

Connection Activity Counseling With the role of cadres in providing Prevention of DHF in Bandung City

Based on results analysis obtained that There is significant relationship between activity counseling with role cadre. Active cadre give counseling by 59%, with activity counseling cadre give information related method do prevention dengue fever as well with counseling so will there is change behavior in society. Change behavior public supported by factors amplifier Where in study This that is counseling health from jumantik. counseling health This will motivating public do PSN with 3M plus so Can create a free territory larva (Green 2005) Behavior is results connection between stimulation or stimulus and response . Behavior is response individual to stimuli, whether they originate from outside nor from in himself. Stimulation or internal stimulus study This is counseling health about prevention and control DHF disease either originates from officer jumantik nor from electronic media or source information other. Whereas response to this stimulus is implementation effort eradication flick with increase cleanliness by the community so ABJ will increase surpass index national (Adnan and Siswani 2019) . In research This cadre Already do activity

The Role of Cadres in Providing Prevention of Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) in Bandung City

counseling preventing dengue fever with using 3M plus but Still many people perceive that fogging is the most appropriate action to overcome dengue fever.

CONCLUSION

In research This factor risk role cadre in do activity prevention of disease fever dengue bleeding is level knowledge, examination flick mosquitoes and activities counseling. related factors with activity prevention fever dengue bleeding is level knowledge cadres and activities counseling. second factor This give enough influence big on activities prevention fever dengue bleeding. Factors that don't relate is inspection flick mosquito because society has capable do it yourself in the environment nor each other's house.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adnan, Adhytia Bagus, and Sri Siswani. 2019. "Peran Kader Jumantik Terhadap Perilaku Masyarakat Dalam Upaya Pencegahan Penyakit Demam Berdarah Dengue (Dbd) Di Wilayah Kerja Kelurahan Tebet Timur Tahun 2019." *Jurnal Untuk Masyarakat Sehat (JUKMAS)* 3(2):1–7.
- 2) Dhefiana, dkk. 2023. "Edukasi Pemberantasan Sarang Nyamuk (PSN) Sebagai Upaya Pencegahan DBD." *Kaibon Abhinaya : Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat* 5(1):34–39. doi: 10.30656/ka.v5i1.4537.
- 3) DINKES JABAR. 2021. "Laporan Kinerja Instansi Pemerintah 2020." *Dinkes Jabar* (25):0–227.
- 4) Indah Trisnaniyanti, and Dkk. 2010. "Persepsi Dan Aktifitas Kader PSN DBD Terhadap Pencegahan Dan Pemberantasan Demam Berdarah Dengue." *Berita Kedokteran Masyarakat* 26(3):132–37.
- 5) Kemenkes RI. 2022. *Laporan Tahunan Kemenkes 2022*.
- 6) Natalia, Meytha, J. V. .. Sambuaga, and Marlyn M. Pandean. 2017. "Peran Serta Juru Pemantau Jentik (JUMANTIK) Dengan Keberadaan Jentik Nyamuk Aedes Aegypti Di Kecamatan Kalawat Kabupaten Minahasa Utara." *JKL Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan* 7(April):7–13.
- 7) Pratamawati, Diana Andriyani. 2012. "Peran Juru Pantau Jentik Dalam Sistem Kewaspadaan Dini Demam Berdarah Dengue Di Indonesia." *Kesmas: National Public Health Journal* 6(6):243. doi: 10.21109/kesmas.v6i6.76.
- 8) Siyam, Nur, and Widya Hary Cahyati. 2018. "Penerapan School Based Vector Control (SBVC) Untuk Pencegahan Dan Pengendalian Vektor Penyakit Di Sekolah." *Media Kesehatan Masyarakat Indonesia* 14(1):86. doi: 10.30597/mkmi.v14i1.3715.
- 9) Siyam, Nur, and Widya Hary Cahyati. 2019. "Desa Siaga Demam Berdarah Dengue (Dbd)." *Jurnal Puruhita* 1(1):91–97. doi: 10.15294/puruhita.v1i1.28653.
- 10) SUTRIYAWAN, AGUNG. 2021. "Pencegahan Demam Berdarah Dengue (Dbd) Melalui Pemberantasan Sarang Nyamuk." *Journal of Nursing and Public Health* 9(2):1–10. doi: 10.37676/jnph.v9i2.1788.
- 11) WHO. 2020. *Treatment, Prevention and Control Global Strategy for Dengue Prevention and Control 2*.